

The Beginner's Guide

Developed by: Davey Wreden / Everything Unlimited Ltd.

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Keywords

Artistic Ethics, Cognitive Bias, Critical Thinking, Interpretation, Mental Health, Privacy, Psychology

Figure 1. Screenshot from *The Beginner's Guide* (2015). © Everything Unlimited Ltd. Used under fair use for educational and critical commentary.

Introduction

The Beginner's Guide (see Figure 1) was developed by Davey Wreden and was released on October 1st, 2015 (Steam, n.d.). It tells the story of a narrator, also called Davey, who guides players through the unfinished games of a developer named Coda. Davey interprets the games as a reflection of Coda's struggles, framing them as a cry for help. As the story unfolds, it seems that Davey may have imposed his own views on Coda's work. Central themes include creativity, mental health, artistic interpretation, and the ethics of sharing one's work (art without consent). The game challenges players to reflect on bias, privacy, and boundaries. Because of that, it fits into the context of serious gaming. Although it is not explicitly

instructive, the game encourages critical thinking and emotional engagement by exploring these topics. It prompts players to reflect on them without directly teaching or providing clear answers. This approach is reflected in the gameplay design. Players have to explore a series of incomplete games while listening to the narrator's interpretations, with minimal player interaction. The focus is on storytelling, not challenges. In the context of serious gaming, the target audience includes students and professionals in the arts, game design, mental health, and ethics, as well as individuals interested in exploring themes such as creativity, privacy, and psychology.

Facts

Release date:	01.10.2015
Developer:	Davey Wreden / Everything Unlimited Ltd.
Game type:	Digital
Number of players:	Single player
Format:	Asynchronous
Time frame:	Approximately 1.5 h
Languages:	English, German, French, Spanish, Russian
Environment:	PC (Windows, macOS, SteamOS+Linux) and a Steam account
Material:	no additional material
Price:	9.75 €

Resonance & Criticism

On Steam, a platform where the game can be purchased and played, the overall rating is "Sehr Positiv" (very positive), with 88% of the 17,830 reviews being positive (cf. Steam, n.d.). Expert opinions are also often favourable towards the game. Both the game and its developer, Davey Wreden, have received various placements on different sites (cf. Dale, 2015; cf. Parkin, 2015). Overall, it was nominated for five awards, with innovation and narrative always being key factors (cf. Nunneley, 2016a; cf. Nunneley, 2016b; Most Innovative - IGN's Best of 2015 Guide - IGN, 2016). However, there are also negative voices, such as Brittany Vincent, for example, who writes in her review on Shacknews: "[it] felt extremely forced and silly by the end of it all" (Vincent, 2015).

Game Principle & Process

The Beginner's Guide is a linear game in which players explore short, unfinished games while listening to the narrator's commentary. The interaction is minimal: players can walk, click, or perform simple actions, but they have no control over the story's progression. This lack of control is a deliberate game mechanic that supports the contemplative nature of the experience. Consequently, the game has no explicit objectives, and its purpose is primarily reflective. Players are meant to interpret and think critically about the games and the

narrator's perspective. The absence of feedback or reward systems further emphasises that the player is not meant to “win,” but to reflect. The learning process seems to come from the story and the ongoing reflection on it. The simplicity of the mechanics, which consist primarily of walking through Coda's fragmented game spaces, allows players to fully concentrate on interpreting these environments and the accompanying commentary. This supports learning goals such as critical thinking, interpretation, and emotional engagement. As more of Coda's perspective is revealed (which seems to differ from Davey's), players' interest could be sustained, and the reflection process encouraged. Since the game is single-player, it lacks social interaction. But the mentioned reflection process seems to be something shared afterwards, possibly inviting individual players to share their thoughts and interpretations. The game does not seem to be directly based on specific theories or models. However, it is worth briefly mentioning its parallels to certain literary works. The Beginner's Guide has been described as Kafkaesque and shows similarities to a book by Vladimir Nabokov from 1962, which one scholar referred to as a beginner's guide to *The Beginner's Guide* (cf. Moulthorp, 2020).

Learning Objectives & Educational Fields of Application

The game encourages critical thinking and reflection. The central learning objective is to help players explore concepts related to creativity, narrative structure, and the subjective nature of art. By exploring themes of mental health, frustration, and creative expression, the game promotes emotional understanding and could train empathy. The game also invites participants to question the narrator's perspective, fostering the ability to evaluate and interpret information from multiple viewpoints. One could also argue that the game helps build self-awareness and an understanding of how personal biases affect perceptions, in this case, of Coda's games and, by extension, art in general. This is because it emphasises introspection, encouraging players to reflect on their own interpretations and how they relate to Coda's creations. The game's mechanisms are going hand in hand with those objectives. Especially the storytelling, the narrator's commentary, and the gradual unveiling of Coda's perspective ensure that the learning objectives are met by promoting reflection, critical thinking, and emotional engagement without being obvious.

The mechanics, like walking through Coda's games, are deliberately simple, allowing players to focus on interpreting and reflecting on the narrative rather than on gameplay complexity. This allows for a personalised learning experience, where each player's journey and conclusions may differ, making the learning process more flexible and engaging.

If a teacher intended to run this game with a group, they would need little preparation. They would need to ensure that there are enough computers, one for each student, with Steam accounts set up. Additionally, the fee of 9.75 euros per game must be paid, as the game is not free. It would also be helpful if students had headphones to hear the narration and focus on their individual gameplay. Once these conditions are met, the game essentially runs on its

own, but teachers should adequately prepare for the thematic content to lead a group reflection and discussion afterwards.

Effectiveness

Although there is no direct study on the effectiveness of *The Beginner's Guide* as an educational game, it is still worthwhile to examine user comments to gain a sense of its impact. Even though such comments are not always representative, they still provide at least an impression. In his review on *Rock Paper Shotgun*, John Walker writes about the game: “[...] it made me think, made me worry about people I care about, made me uncomfortable. And for that, I think, it deserves praise” (Walker, 2015). Darren Nakamura says in his review: “More than anything else, it has caused me a lot of introspection, a feat few games ever achieve” (Nakamura, 2015). At least, it seems to fundamentally have the potential to move people and encourage reflection. This impression is supported by research from Bormann and Greitemeyer (2015), who showed that narrative video games can increase players' sense of immersion, which in turn can help satisfy basic psychological needs such as autonomy and relatedness. Their study compared a narrative-driven game with a non-narrative control game and found that players of the narrative game reported higher levels of emotional, cognitive, and narrative immersion (Bormann & Greitemeyer, 2015). Although the study did not focus specifically on *The Beginner's Guide*, it supports the idea that the emotional and reflective responses reported by its players align with the general effects observed in story-driven games.

Further research examining *The Beginner's Guide* directly would be valuable, especially given that the game relies almost entirely on storytelling as its primary mode of engagement. Another interesting aspect of *The Beginner's Guide* is that players do not need to adapt to different difficulty levels to keep the gameplay engaging. Furthermore, an article on the subject even states: “Action in the game is so railed-in that it approaches not free play but its opposite, recorded video” (Moulthorp, 2020). Nevertheless, this does not necessarily affect engagement. In this case, it is the storyline that keeps players engaged and gradually immerses them mentally into the game's world.

Potentially Problematic Aspects

Overall, no problematic aspects of the game are apparent, but a trigger warning might still be appropriate. After all, the game deals with topics like depression and anxiety without revealing much beforehand about what it is actually about. In the description on Steam, it simply says, “[...] it tells the story of a person struggling to deal with something they do not understand” (Steam, n.d.). For some people, these topics can be deeply moving, and they may want to consider whether they are ready to engage with them.

Reviewer(s): Saskia Sterzl, Johannes Katsarov

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